

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**AN OBSERVATIONAL STUDY TO KNOW THE PREVALENCE
AND ETIOLOGY OF NOSOCOMIAL INFECTIONS IN
PATIENTS OF MEDICINE UNIT OF NISHTAR HOSPITAL**¹Dr Nawal Fatima, ²Dr Samreen Khalid, ³Dr Shahwali¹MO at DHQ Hospital, Dera Ghazi Khan, ²Isra University, Islamabad
Sheikh Zayed University, Khost Afghanistan.**Article Received:** May 2019**Accepted:** June 2019**Published:** July 2019**Abstract:**

Purpose: To evaluate the frequency of hospital infections in patients admitted to the medical Units of Nishtar Hospital, Multan and know the causing factors in these patients.

Study design: An Observational study.

Location and duration of study: This study was conducted in the Medicine Units of Nishtar Hospital, Multan for one year duration from March 2018 to February 2019.

Method: More than 12 years of age patients were included who were admitted for more than 48 hours working on clinical evidence of infection.

Results: In the study period, 135 of 1197 patients had nosocomial infection. The frequency of hospital infections was 11,278%. Cutaneous infection (IV in situ bronchitis) 59 (43.703%), respiratory tract infection, 23 (17 037%) were observed, 31 (22 962%) and infection urinary tract infection 11 (8.148%). Other infections we identified were 11 (8.148%) in soft tissue, gastrointestinal tract and wound infections.

Conclusion: Patients admitted to the medical unit have a higher risk of developing a nosocomial infection from various methods. It is supposed that sterilization, disinfection of instruments, proper nursing care and careful management of invasive procedures and equipments are also good tools against life-threatening infections.

Key words: Hospital infections, nosocomial infection.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Nawal Fatima,**

MO at DHQ Hospital, Dera Ghazi Khan.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Nawal Fatima et al., *An Observational Study to Know the Prevalence and Etiology of Nosocomial Infections in Patients of Medicine Unit of Nishtar Hospital.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(07).

INTRODUCTION:

Hospital infection is describe as an infection developed after hospitalization in 48 hours or 48 hours after incubation. It has been shown that patients presenting in Medical ward have a high prevalence rate of 11.24% high risk of nosocomial infection. Hospital infections are caused by viral, fungal and bacterial pathogens. The pathogens most commonly observed are staphylococcus, mycobacterium tuberculi, E-coli, aspergillus, candida, trichosporon, malassezia, fusarium and pseudomonas. All are linked with higher mortality and morbidity. Measures to stop nosocomial infection in Medical ward include hand washing before and after contact with the patient and during breathing intubation, during catheter insertion aseptic technique should be observed, and immediate removal of non-necessary catheters. The aim of this analysis was to know the prevalence and nosocomial infection pattern in patients admitted to our Medical ward and to identify the etiologic agent in these cases.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

This hospital-based observational study was conducted in the Medicine Units of Nistar Hospital, Multan for one year duration from March 2018 to

February 2019. All patients over 12 years of age admitted to the Medical Unit II for above 48 hours and had developed clinical presentation of infection and clinical tests that confirms the diagnosis of the patient were selected for the analysis. These patients admitted via OPD or hospital emergency department. Patients admitted for less than 48 hours were excluded from the analysis. A designed proforma for data collection was used. The patients detailed history was obtained and a complete clinical examination was done. Patients were evaluated on a daily basis to evaluate the treatment response and to establish new infection development and its evidence. The temperature table was also recorded and it was regularly maintained. All baseline investigations were performed, including whole blood, blood glucose levels, urine analysis and chest x-ray image. According to the patients clinical presentation, a large number of studies were performed. The Prevalence was evaluated by the number of patients gaining infection; While the pattern was confirmed by the obtained infection type, the causing agents were evaluated by identifying the sources or pathogens causing infection. Data were recorded and analyzed in SPSS version 18.0 and frequencies, percentages, mean $\pm$ SD were calculated.

Relative Frequency of Nosocomial Infections

Source: Data from CDC, National Nosocomial Infection Surveillance.

PLAY

Mastering: Nosocomial Infections - Overview

Table 14.5

RESULTS:

During the study, 135 of 1197 patients had nosocomial infections. The frequency of hospital infections was 11.27%. Skin infection (IV in situ bronchitis) were observed in 59 (43.703%) and respiratory tract infection in 23 (17.037%), UTI in 31 (22.962%) and blood circulation infection in 11 (8.148%) patients. Other infections we identified were 11 (8.148%) in soft tissue, wound and gastrointestinal tract infections. Send appropriate samples of the involved area (blood, urine, sputum, branula catheter Foley catheter) to detect potential organisms. In most of the examples we could not

identify the possible organism because the microbiology department of the hospital was not in the correct order. However, some specimens shows E.coli have been found in of urinary tract infections, branulitis Staphylococcus aureus in skin infections in respiratory tract infections (mouth ulcers) pneumococcus, Pseudomonas and klebsiala Staphylococcus epidermidus. We describe enterococci in the blood culture of several patients. No organism was found in the stool culture of the patients who developed diarrhea 48 hours after hospitalization.

DISCUSSION:

For patients with venous catheter (insertion branula), urinary bladder catheterization and stopping barriers during wound treatment, patients admitted to a medical unit with a risk of hospital infection I (patients with mouth ulcers). Medical device is the most common hospital infection followed by

branulitis, urinary tract infection, pneumonia and primary infection. Common infections detected in our study were branulitis, catheter, bloodstream infection, respiratory tract infection, wound infection and gastrointestinal infections and soft tissue related urinary tract infection.

The prevalence of nosocomial infection reported in this analysis was 12.27%. The most frequent and common nosocomial infection in the intravenous catheterization area is brucellitis. In our study, 31 patients (22,962%) were diagnosed with urinary tract infection. The source of nosocomial UTIs was the placement of the Foley catheter using non-sterile techniques. Richards observes that IU are responsible for 22-31% of hospital infections in the medical / surgical intensive care unit National Hospital Infections Surveillance (NNIS, for its abbreviation in English) reported in the database. Finklestein and colleagues reported an incidence of 11% to 15% among 338 patients in a single Israeli ICU. Rosser and his colleagues have found that age (over 49 years) and catheterization are independent factors linked with the development of hospital UTI. Nosocomial pneumonia is the second most common nosocomial infection in critically ill patients and is the main cause of deaths due to hospital acquired infection. Klebsiella pneumoniae has also shown that infection occurs in the bloodstream, while a study in Brazil showed that another study has caused bloodstream infections in the US and Canada among ten major pathogens.

CONCLUSION:

In this observational study, we found that patients are at the risk of grabbing hospital infection admitted to Medical ward. Common hospital infections identified in our study were hospital pneumonia, bloodstream infections and urinary tract infections (UTI). We emphasize mutual co-operation between health care workers and the hospital in accordance with standard

guidelines for preventing infection in the hospital, and in public opinion.

REFERENCES:

1. Aouf, A., Gueddi, T., Djeghout, B. and Ammari, H., 2018. Frequency and susceptibility pattern of uropathogenic Enterobacteriaceae isolated from patients in Algiers, Algeria. *The Journal of Infection in Developing Countries*, 12(04), pp.244-249.
2. Sánchez-García JM, Sorlózano-Puerto A, Navarro-Marí JM, Fernández JG. Evolution of the antibiotic-resistance of microorganisms causing urinary tract infections: A 4-year epidemiological surveillance study in a hospital population. *Revista Clínica Española* (English Edition). 2018 Oct 26.
3. Rahimi-Bashar, Farshid, Pezhman Karami, Azad Khaledi, Akram Dehghan, Mohamad Ali Seifrabie, and Mojtaba Hedayat Yaghoobi. "Evaluation of the Prevalence of Nosocomial Infection in Different Wards of Be'sat Hospital of Hamedan." *Avicenna Journal of Clinical Microbiology and Infection* 5, no. 2 (2018): 31-35.
4. Meyer, Christian Niels, Karin Armbruster, Michael Kemp, Trine Rolighed Thomsen, and Ram Benny Dessau. "Pleural infection: a retrospective study of clinical outcome and the correlation to known etiology, co-morbidity and treatment factors." *BMC pulmonary medicine* 18, no. 1 (2018): 160.
5. Costa, T., Linhares, I., Ferreira, R., Neves, J. and Almeida, A., 2018. Frequency and Antibiotic Resistance of Bacteria Implicated in Community

- Urinary Tract Infections in North Aveiro Between 2011 and 2014. *Microbial Drug Resistance*, 24(4), pp.493-504.
6. Yaghoobi, Mojtaba Hedayat, Mohammad Reza Arabestani, Pezhman Karami, Azad Khaledi, Mohamad Ali Seifrabie, Omid Khiabanchian, and Farshid Rahimi-Bashar. "The pattern of antibiotic resistance of common bacteria causing nosocomial infections." *Middle East Journal of Family Medicine* 7, no. 10 (2018): 19.
 7. Badve, Monica S., Zien Zhou, Diederik van de Beek, Craig S. Anderson, and Maree L. Hackett. "Frequency of post-stroke pneumonia: Systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies." *International Journal of Stroke* (2018): 1747493018806196.
 8. Farid, Golnar Abbasi, Ahmad Bagheri Moghaddam, and Amin Bojdy. "Nosocomial Pneumonia in Patients Admitted to the Intensive Care Unit of a Tertiary Care Center in Mashhad, Northeast of Iran; an Etiologic Survey." *Archives of Clinical Infectious Diseases* 13, no. 4 (2018).
 9. Paula, Milena Cristina de, Rachel M. Monteiro, Pedro CA Domingues, Paula Regina S. Hermann, Denise de Andrade, Adriano M. Ferreira, and Evandro Watanabe. "Frequency and carbapenems susceptibility profile of non-fermenting Gram-negative bacilli isolated from clinical samples between 2007 and 2012." *Jornal Brasileiro de Patologia e Medicina Laboratorial* 54, no. 1 (2018): 5-8.
 10. Vijay, Gnanaguru, Anirban Mandal, Jhuma Sankar, Arti Kapil, Rakesh Lodha, and S. K. Kabra. "Ventilator Associated Pneumonia in Pediatric Intensive Care Unit: Incidence, Risk Factors and Etiological Agents." *The Indian Journal of Pediatrics* (2018): 1-6.
 11. Ghashghaee, A., Behzadifar, M., Azari, S., Farhadi, Z., Bragazzi, N.L., Behzadifar, M., Shahri, S.S.S., Ghaemmohamadi, M.S., Ebadi, F., Mohammadibakhsh, R. and Seyedin, H., 2018. Prevalence of nosocomial infections in Iran: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Medical journal of the Islamic Republic of Iran*, 32, p.48.
 12. Male PV, kumar Kashyap M, Bora RA, Kshirsagar VV. Ventilator associated pneumonia (VAP) in an intensive care unit of a tertiary care hospital: incidence, their microbial etiology, risk factors and role of multidrug resistant pathogens. *INDIAN JOURNAL OF APPLIED RESEARCH*. 2018 Nov 6;7(2).
 13. Parihar, Gajendra Singh, Vaibhav Misra, Shashi Gandhi, and Pramod Kushwaha. "ISOLATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF ENTEROCOCCUS FROM VARIOUS CLINICAL SAMPLES IN TERTIARY CARE INSTUTE WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO VRE (VANCOMYCIN RESISTANT ENTEROCOCCUS) AND VISE (VANCOMYCIN INTERMEDIATE SENSITIVE ENTEROCOCCUS)." *INDIAN JOURNAL OF APPLIED RESEARCH* 8, no. 4 (2018).
 14. Hwang, Ji-won, Seung Woo Park, Eun Jeong Cho, Ga Yeon Lee, Eun Kyoung Kim, Sung-A. Chang, Sung-Ji Park et al. "Risk factors for poor prognosis in nosocomial infective endocarditis." *The Korean journal of internal medicine* 33, no. 1 (2018): 102.
 15. Na, Soo Jin, Chi Ryang Chung, Hee Jung Choi, Yang Hyun Cho, Jeong Hoon Yang, Gee Young Suh, and Kyeongman Jeon. "Blood Stream Infection in Patients on Venovenous Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation for Respiratory Failure." *Infection Control & Hospital Epidemiology* (2018): 1-4.